

Modelling Decarbonisation Pathways in the Power Sector: The Case of South Africa

Nosaibeh Nosrati Ghods, ESRG, South Africa
Savanha de Kock, ESRG, South Africa
Jacqueline Siphokazi Gongxeka, Eskom, South Africa
Usisipho Gogela, ESRG, South Africa

30 May 2024

Keywords: Energy System Modeling, GHG Emissions Reduction, Energy Planning, OSeMOSYS, Climate-Related Pressures, Renewable Energy.

Acknowledgements

This report was produced during the EMPA-24 programme organized by the Climate Compatible Growth, United Nations Energy Commission for Africa, Ministry of Energy Ghana, the Ghana Energy Commission, Ghana Atomic Energy Commission, Ghana Institute of Management and Public Administration, and The Brew-Hammond Energy Centre at Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology as the organizers of the EMP-A.

We would like to thank the CCG for comprehensively funding our participation. We would also like to thank Rudolf Yeganyan, Fernando A. Plazas Niño, Simone Osei-Owusu, Pedro Peters, Koshikwinja Matabishi, and the whole team from Climate Compatible Growth for their support in the development of this work.

This material has been produced with support from the Climate Compatible Growth (CCG) programme. CCG is funded by UK aid from the UK government. However, the views expressed herein do not necessarily reflect the UK government's official policies.

Executive Summary

South Africa's energy landscape is marked by numerous challenges and opportunities. Key challenges include electricity supply constraints, escalating electricity costs for consumers, widespread energy poverty, and a dominant reliance on coal across both supply and demand sectors. Fortunately, energy systems models offer a valuable solution, enabling the exploration of sustainable development pathways that effectively address these complex challenges and more (Hughes et al., 2020).

This research considers three scenarios - Business as Usual, Net Zero 2050, and Integrated Resource Plan 2023 - to investigate using OSeMOSYS. OSeMOSYS is an open-source programming language and solver. This modelling research shows that if South Africa's power system continues under no climate-related pressures, it could pose significant health risks and contribute to climate change through the Business as Usual (BAU) scenario. Across all three scenarios, total CO₂ emissions decrease in tandem with the rate of coal power reduction, potentially driven by coal's high costs relative to alternative technologies, a trend not predicted by the model for the foreseeable future.

Interestingly, the results demonstrate that the Integrated Resource Plan 2023 has lower CO₂ emissions than Business as Usual. In the case of total decarbonization in the Net Zero 2050 scenario, the total investment cost would be approximately \$220 million more than in Business as Usual scenario. All scenarios require substantial investment, approximately US\$178 billion, which shows the potential of allowing the model to solve for the cost-optimal emission reduction curves, specifically NZ2050 scenario in the future. However, the most cost-effective scenario is the Integrated Resource Plan 2023. Therefore, it is highly suggested to expand the IRP23 scenario to implement various build limits on renewable energy technologies in earlier years, investigate coal fleet EAF recovery scenarios, and assess varying degrees of penetration of gas technologies.

1. Introduction

Energy system modeling is a crucial tool to inform policymakers and scientists about the many routes that may be taken to achieve certain goals, such as achieving environmental goals (reducing GHG emissions) and economic goals. The first oil crisis (1973) and growing interest in energy concerns led to the development of energy system models, which have been around for almost 50 years. Since then, the quantity and complexity of models have rapidly risen (Connolly et al., 2010; Löffler et al., 2017).

OSeMOSYS serves as a helpful and clear tool for informing energy planning, as it easily allows testing novel applications and formulations (Howells et al., 2011). It builds on an open source programming language (GNU MathProg (Makhorin, 2008) and solver (GLPK (Makhorin, 2012))). This research focuses on three distinct scenarios in South Africa: Business as Usual (BAU), Net ZERO 2050 (NZ2050), and Integrated Resource Plan 2023 (IRP23), each of which will be thoroughly discussed in the subsequent sections. The aim of this research is to determine how South Africa's power system would evolve under no climate-related pressures through the BAU scenario. Furthermore, this research investigates whether the pathway proposed in the national IRP23 has a better energy future for South Africa than the BAU scenario. Finally, the power sector is investigated under an ambitious GHG budget of 8Gt and increasing emissions penalties in the NZ2050 scenario.

2. Methodology and Scenario Development

2.1 Methodology

TIMES, MESSAGE, MARKAL, OSeMOSYS are examples of modeling software with lower temporal resolutions, over a longer period (usually in the range of years or decades) (Qa, 2022; Vimmerstedt et al., 2022) which could analyse problems related to the adequacy of energy system better.

In this work Osemosys Cloud and clicSAND software are used for constructing and executing the model as well as for visualising and analysing the outcomes (Cannone et al., 2022).

Three scenarios are selected for this research: (i) Business as Usual, (ii) Net Zero 2050, and (iii) IRP23, which are explained in detail in the following sections of this report. The required data gathered for primary energy, power sector and demands in South Africa for various sources such as coal, biomass, OCGT, solar, wind, hydropower etc. were used to accomplish the aims of this research. The data was organized into an Excel Workbook consisting of multiple tabs, allowing the user to gather and manipulate data from multiple sources and organise it into a user-friendly format in a single open collection. The data is ready for analysts to use, regardless of the energy modeling software they choose, even though it was designed to be fully compatible with clicSAND software (Cannone, Allington, De Wet, et al., 2022) for the Open Source energy Modelling SYStem – OSeMOSYS (Howells et al., 2011).

Defaults OSeMOSYS values were used for these parameters: Depreciation Method = 1; Discount Rate = 0.1; Year Split = 1/96 for all 96-time slices which was reduced for this study to 8 slices so that they are of equal length (Cannone, Allington, Charbonnier, et al., 2022).

Technology costs (FOM, VOM, Capital costs) as well as capacity factors for the years 2020 to 2050 were taken from Meridian Economics' Comparative Analysis of IRP 2023 cost assumptions, and associated costs data sheet (Meridian, 2024)..

Region-specific efficiencies for power transmission and distribution were calculated from electricity demand, electricity import, electricity export (DMRE (Republic of South Africa), 2024) and electricity generation (EMBER, 2018; Eskom Ltd., 2022; Pierce & Le Roux, 2023).

Default OSeMOSYS values were used for the Capacity-to-Activity unit; for more information on default data (CCG, 2022). Operational lifetimes and capacity factors for fossil, biomass, nuclear and gas were taken from Meridian Economics (Meridian, 2024). The capacity factors for wind, solar, and

hydropower technologies for South Africa were used (Brinkerink, Gallachóir & Deane, 2021; Ninja, 2024).

The data for emissions factors was collected (National Treasury, 2022) which is explained more in the sections to follow.

After collecting all the data, the next step was to transfer all the data to the modelling tool selected for the analysis. To develop a model that the solver can analyze to discover the best answer in terms of cost and environmental condition, the user adds data to an Excel workbook called the SAND Interface in the clicSAND program. This file contains all the OSeMOSYS parameters (Connone, 2020).

2.2 Assumptions

Collected data for electricity imports and exports show small discrepancies between Eskom and DMRE (Eskom Ltd., 2022; DMRE (Republic of South Africa), 2024); therefore, the lower and higher values of the data were considered as the lower and higher bounds in the model. Projected data was calculated. The installed capacity of biomass from 2018 to 2022 was also assumed. The electricity capacity and generation of pumped storage of hydropower was considered in hydropower plants. The electricity generation of hydropower from 2015-2017 was assumed.

2.3 Scenarios

Three scenarios were modelled for South Africa's power system to explore possible future pathways and assess decarbonisation measures through the implementation of various model parameters, including integrating existing policies, emissions constraints and penalties, and reliable cost projections.

2.3.1 Business As Usual

The Business-As-Usual (BAU) scenario serves as a reference point for our analysis. It represents a continuation of current trends and policies without any significant interventions aimed at decarbonization or technological advancement.

The key characteristics of this scenario are as follows:

Least-cost pathway to meet demand projections prioritizing cost-effectiveness in energy generation without additional constraints or considerations. The energy mix in this scenario is heavily influenced

by historical capacities. This means a continued reliance on existing coal-fired power plants and other conventional energy sources. The scenario assumes that the current intensity of energy policies remains unchanged. No new significant policies or regulatory measures are introduced to alter the existing energy landscape. There are no additional constraints or targets for reducing greenhouse gas emissions. The focus remains on meeting energy demand with the least-cost resources available. The scenario does not incorporate any new energy efficiency measures beyond those already in place. It assumes that current practices and efficiencies remain constant.

The primary objective of the BAU scenario is to ensure that energy demand is met at the lowest possible cost, relying on the existing infrastructure and technologies. By maintaining the status quo, this scenario aims to provide stability and predictability in the energy sector without introducing new variables or uncertainties. The BAU scenario provides a benchmark against which other scenarios can be compared. It highlights the potential outcomes if South Africa continues on its current path without significant policy shifts or investments in new technologies. This scenario serves as a critical reference for understanding the implications of maintaining existing practices versus pursuing more ambitious and transformative energy strategies.

2.3.2 Modelling the Integrated Resource Plan 2023 Builds

The IRP23 scenario was developed to evaluate the effectiveness of South Africa's Integrated Resource Plan 2023 (IRP 2023) in achieving its primary objectives. These objectives include ensuring the security of energy supply, considering environmental impacts, and managing the total cost of supply (Mccall et al., 2019). Additionally, the scenario proposes an alternative pathway to better meet these criteria.

The following objectives and goals were considered:

Security of Supply: Ensuring a stable and reliable energy supply to meet the projections of growing demand is a critical objective. The scenario assesses the ability of the IRP 2023 to maintain energy security through diverse energy sources.

Environmental Considerations: Reducing greenhouse gas emissions and minimizing the environmental footprint of the energy sector are key priorities. The scenario evaluates the environmental impact of the proposed energy mix and its alignment with climate goals.

Cost Management: Balancing the need for new investments with the goal of keeping electricity affordable for consumers and sustainable for the economy is essential. The scenario explores cost-effective alternatives.

Evaluation and Alternative Pathways: The IRP23 scenario explores alternative pathways that might offer improved outcomes. Including increasing the share of renewable energy sources in the energy mix, reducing reliance on fossil fuels, particularly coal and gas.

Several constraints and assumptions are integral to this scenario:

Eskom’s 2035 Coal Decommissioning Schedule: The scenario adheres to Eskom's planned schedule for decommissioning several coal-fired power plants by 2035. This schedule reflects the need to phase out aging and less efficient coal infrastructure.

Committed Capacities: The IRP23 scenario includes committed new capacities from various energy sources that are either under construction or have been procured. These capacities are Wind: 784 MW, Solar PV: 2115 MW, Gas: 1220 MW, New Coal: 1440 MW.

Realistic Renewable Energy (RE) New Build Rates: The scenario incorporates realistic build rates for new renewable energy projects. These rates take into account the logistical, financial, and regulatory constraints that could impact the deployment speed of renewable technologies (Meridian Economics (2024)).

We did not distinguish between Horizon 1 and Horizon 2 as in the national IRP 2023, but rather performed an optimisation analysis over the whole model horizon. Similarly technology costs have been updated to reflect more reasonable cost projections that include reductions over time and the cost of unserved energy was not considered as it was assumed the power sector could meet demand and ensure security of supply (Meridian Economics (2024)).

Table 2.3.2.1: Utility scale, rooftop solar PV and onshore wind annual new build capacity upper limits:

Model Period	Annual New Capacity (GW)	
	Utility scale and rooftop solar PV	Onshore wind
2026-2029	5	2
2030-2034	5	2
2035-2039	10	3
2040-2044	10	4
2045-2050	10	5

2.3.3 Net Zero CO₂ 2050

The aim of this scenario was to develop and characterise a long-term emission pathway for South Africa to reach net zero CO₂ emissions by 2050 in terms of the trajectories of energy supply technologies and the costs associated with this transition.

For the choice of a singular total model period emissions budget, the ambitious 8Gt cumulative GHG budget was selected to provide insight into the most stringent measures necessary to achieve net zero emissions (Marquard et al., 2023). This selection aims to assess a pathway consistent with South Africa's obligations under the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change and the Paris Agreement (Mccall et al., 2020). While achieving a truly long-term net-zero pathway necessitates shifting away from GHG-intensive activities across all sectors, this analysis highlights the importance of transformation in the electricity sector (Marquard et al., 2023). By setting such an ambitious target, the model can identify the highest-impact strategies and technologies required to meet these stringent limits.

The *Model Period Emission Limit* parameter establishes an upper emissions limit for the entire model period while allowing the model to determine the cost-optimal emission reduction curve. This approach resulted in accelerated decarbonization efforts from 2045 to 2050, which were characterized by unrealistically high annual new build rates for the selected technologies. This acceleration was attributed to the projected decline in the capital costs of renewable generation technologies over time.

As such an linearly-approximated *Annual Emission Limit* was introduced to ensure a smooth decarbonisation of the power sector and promote a resilient zero-emission capacity mix post 2050 and beyond.

This scenario further implemented an *Emissions Penalty* per unit of CO₂ emission informed by the South African government plans to increase the nation's emissions penalty by US\$1/tonne CO₂eq annually to reach US\$20/tonne CO₂eq by 2026 and US\$120/tonne CO₂eq in 2050 and beyond. Additionally, tax-free allowances will be progressively reduced from January 2026, to December 2030 to enhance the impact of the carbon tax. (National Treasury, 2022) This parameter disincentivizes the model from producing emissions by taxing each unit of emission released, thus technologies may emit freely but it becomes increasingly costly.

Table 2.3.3.1: Emissions penalties implemented in the NZ2050 scenario.

Year	Carbon Tax (US\$/tonne)	Carbon Tax (ZAR/tonne)
Current (Official)	~US \$8/t	~R 144/t
Current (with allowances)	~US \$1.66/t	~R 30/t
2026	US \$20/t	R 360/t
2030	US \$30/t	R 541/t
>2050	US \$120/t	R 2165.48/t

This approach aims to illuminate the scale of transformation needed and the importance of robust and effective policies, and further aims to provide a clear roadmap for the most ambitious measures required.

3. Results

The results of the three scenarios are investigated and compared in the following sections. The installed capacity, power generation, CO₂ emissions (to assess environmental conditions), and total investment costs (to assess economic) are highlighted.

Figure 3.1: Total Annual Capacity (GW) 2015-2050 by technology for each of the three scenarios.

All scenarios implement significant amounts of solar and wind. All scenarios phase down coal, but at different rates.

Figure 3.1 illustrates the installed capacity of each of the generation technologies. Similarly to the power generation findings, solar and onshore wind constitute the majority of installed capacity. In the BAU scenario, coal decreases as plants reach the end of operational life during the model period, yet a significant amount of coal remains part of the capacity beyond 2050, with a small amount of gas also included in this scenario.

In the IRP2023 scenario, coal power plants are retired more quickly than in the BAU scenario and are replaced by gas. In the NZ2050 scenario, biomass is incorporated into the total capacity to supplement renewable energy as the last coal power plant units are shut down. Additionally, starting in 2045, more nuclear capacity is added to the NZ2050 to provide base load generation capabilities as coal and gas power plants are retired.

Figure 3.2: Power Generation (GW) 2015-2050 by technology for each of the three scenarios.

As shown in Figure 3.2, the Business as Usual (BAU) Scenario, without climate-related pressures, continues to rely heavily on coal towards 2050, but no gas appears in this unconstrained mix. In contrast, the IRP23 Scenario incorporates more renewables, but also includes significant adoption of gas, unlike the BAU Scenario (Figure 3.2). Gas may provide a measure of insurance against unpredictable coal fleet performance. The Net Zero 2050 (NZ2050) Scenario achieves the highest penetration of wind and solar, complemented by approximately 13 GW of nuclear power for baseload generation in 2050, resulting in an increased total investment cost.

Figure 3.3: Annual Emissions (kt CO₂) in each of the three scenarios.

Total emissions (kt CO₂) decline in all three scenarios, proportionally to the rate at which coal power declines, which could be due to the high cost of coal compared to other technologies, as not predicted by the model for the upcoming years (Figure 3.3). By 2050, the BAU scenario reaches 90 Mt CO₂, the IRP scenario reaches 70 Mt CO₂, and the NZ scenario reaches 0 CO₂ emissions.

Figure 3.4: Total investment cost in each of the scenarios (BAU, IRP23, NZ2050)

All scenarios require substantial investment: approximately US \$178 billion. Net Zero scenario is only US \$230 million more than the proposed IRP scenario, for the most ambitious decarbonisation efforts.

4. Discussion

In the BAU scenario, as South Africa's power system evolves without climate-related pressures, it will predominantly rely on coal, leading to high greenhouse gas emissions. Although there will still be significant growth in solar and wind technologies due to declining costs and technological advancements over the model horizon. However, continuing with a business as usual approach is a high risk strategy since climate change disproportionately affects vulnerable communities and risks health issues, economic instability, and displacement (Leichenko and Silva, 2014).

Based on the results of our modelling exercise, several policy insights emerge that can guide the future development of South Africa's power sector:

- (i) Encourage a diverse energy mix to ensure energy security and economic stability, even in the absence of climate pressures.
- (ii) Provide economic incentives for renewable energy investments to leverage their cost-effectiveness and environmental benefits.
- (iii) Invest in R&D for cleaner coal technologies and carbon capture and storage to mitigate the environmental impact of coal if it is to be used to a great extent in future.

The pathway proposed in the national Integrated Resource Plan 2023 is not the optimal energy future for South Africa. While it includes renewable energy penetration due to cost advantages, it also relies significantly on gas as a baseload replacement for coal, resulting in emissions that are still too high to align with South Africa's commitment to the Paris Agreement.

Our analysis has highlighted several important policy insights that can effectively guide the development and transformation of South Africa's power sector:

- (i) Revisit and revise the Integrated Resource Plan 2023 to align with more ambitious emission reduction targets, incorporating higher shares of renewables and lower reliance on gas.
- (ii) Reliable Integrated Resource Planning: Ensure integrated planning that is optimised and considers the economic, environmental, and social dimensions to achieve a sustainable and low-carbon energy future.

Achieving net-zero CO₂ emissions by 2050 under an ambitious GHG budget of 8Gt and increasing emissions penalties necessitates the highest penetration of wind and solar energy technologies, complemented by approximately 13GW of nuclear power for baseload as coal is phased out by 2045. From our modelling results, we can derive several key policy insights that are crucial for shaping the future of South Africa's power sector if we are to achieve our most ambitious emissions reduction targets by 2050:

(i) Accelerate the deployment of renewables, urgently address the grid capacity constraints and implement policies that rapidly accelerate the deployment to achieve deep decarbonization.

(ii) Consider significant investments in technologies to complement renewables and provide a reliable baseload, ensuring grid stability as coal is phased out. This model in its current iteration does not assess energy storage systems and flexibility measures, however these technologies would likely be extremely beneficial (Davis et al., 2018, IRENA, 2015).

(iii) Implement Just Transition Frameworks and support mechanisms for communities and workers affected by the coal phase-out (Presidential Climate Commission, 2022).

These policy insights aim to guide South Africa towards a more sustainable energy future while addressing the socio-economic impacts of the energy transition.

5. Conclusion

This study explores three scenarios - Business as Usual (BAU), Net Zero 2050 (NZ2050), and South Africa's Integrated Resource Plan 2023 (IRP23).

This research aims to assess how South Africa's power system would develop in the absence of climate-related constraints, using the BAU scenario as a reference point.

Additionally, this research compares the energy future of South Africa under the national IRP23 plan with the BAU scenario, to determine which pathway is more beneficial.

Lastly, the power sector is examined under the NZ2050 scenario, which assumes an ambitious greenhouse gas reduction target of 8Gt and increasing emissions penalties.

6. Future work

Develop fully disaggregated supply and demand sectors for detailed full-sector energy system analysis and include Sasol and refineries, energy storage systems and flexibility measures, as well as grid constraints. Requiring an update and expansion of the CCG's South African Starter Data Kit.

Expand the IRP23 scenario to assess more optimistic and pessimistic build limits on RE technologies in earlier years (2024-2030), investigate coal fleet EAF recovery scenarios and implement varying degrees of penetration of gas technologies. As well as perform more detailed comparison of modelled IRP scenarios with South Africa's official IRP 2023 results.

We would also like to further expand the NZ2050 scenario to assess total model period emission limits only and allow the model to solve for the cost-optimal emission reduction-curves, assess a range of GHG budgets and varying emissions penalties as a result of international pressures.

References

1. Brinkerink, M., Gallachóir, B. & Deane, P. 2021. Building and Calibrating a Country-Level Detailed Global Electricity Model Based on Public Data. *Energy Strategy Reviews*. 33(July 2020). DOI: 10.1016/j.esr.2020.100592.
 2. Cannone, C., Allington, L., De Wet, N., Goynes, P., Valderrama, C., Kapor, V., Wright, J., Yeganyan, R., et al. 2022. *clicSAND for OSeMOSYS: a user-friendly interface using open-source optimisation software for energy system modelling analysis*. Available: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9325-8147><https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7957-8451>.
 3. Cannone, C., Allington, L., Charbonnier, F., Walker, M.Z. & Halloran, C. 2022. Designing a zero-order energy transition model : a guide for creating a Starter Data Kit. 1–17.
 4. CCG. 2022. *Energy and Flexibility Modelling: OSeMOSYS & FlexTool*.
 5. Connolly, D., Lund, H., Mathiesen, B. V. & Leahy, M. 2010. A review of computer tools for analysing the integration of renewable energy into various energy systems. *Applied Energy*. 87(4):1059–1082. DOI: 10.1016/j.apenergy.2009.09.026.
 6. Connone, C. 2020. Master in Energy Engineering Towards evidence-based policymaking : energy modelling tools for sustainable development Escola Tècnica Superior d'Enginyeria Industrial de Barcelona. (October).
 7. Davis, S.J., Lewis, N.S., Shaner, M., Aggarwal, S., Arent, D., Azevedo, I.L., Benson, S.M., Bradley, T., Brouwer, J., Chiang, Y.-M., Clack, C.T.M., Cohen, A., Doig, S., Edmonds, J., Fennell, P., Field, C.B., Hannegan, B., Hodge, B.-M., Hoffert, M.I. and Ingersoll, E. (2018). Net-zero emissions energy systems. *Science*, [online] 360(6396). doi:<https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aas9793>.
 8. DMRE (Republic of South Africa). 2024. *Statistics*.
 9. EMBER. 2018. *South Africa Electricity*. Available: https://www.indexmundi.com/south_africa/electricity_exports.html.
 10. Eskom Ltd. 2022. *Eskom Data Portal*. Available: <https://www.eskom.co.za/dataportal/>.
 11. Howells, M., Rogner, H., Strachan, N., Heaps, C., Huntington, H., Kypreos, S., Hughes, A., Silveira, S., et al. 2011. OSeMOSYS: The Open Source Energy Modeling System. An introduction to its ethos, structure and development. *Energy Policy*. 39(10):5850–5870. DOI: 10.1016/j.enpol.2011.06.033.
 12. Hughes, A., Merven, B., McCall, B., Ahjum, F., Caetano, T., Hartley, F., Ireland, G., Burton, J., et al. 2020. Evolution, Assumptions and Architecture of the South African Energy Systems Model SATIM. *Energy Systems Research Group- Working Paper*.
-

-
13. IRENA (2015). From Baseload to Peak Renewables provide a reliable solution. [online] www.irena.org. Available at: <https://www.irena.org/publications/2015/Jun/From-Baseload-to-Peak-Renewables-provide-a-reliable-solution> [Accessed 30 May 2024].
 14. Ireland, G., Hughes, A., Merven, B., Davis, S., Ahjum, F. and Mccall, B. (2019). Combined system-wide value of sectoral electrical demand flexibility in South Africa's integrated energy system: an application in SATIM. [online] Available at: https://ebe.uct.ac.za/sites/default/files/content_migration/ebe_uct_ac_za/1135/files/2019_Flexible_Demand_Paper2.pdf [Accessed 30 May 2024].
 15. Leichenko, R. and Silva, J.A. (2014). Climate change and poverty: vulnerability, impacts, and alleviation strategies. *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Climate Change*, 5(4), pp.539–556. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1002/wcc.287>.
 16. Löffler, K., Hainsch, K., Burandt, T., Oei, P.Y., Kemfert, C. & Von Hirschhausen, C. 2017. Designing a model for the global energy system-GENeSYS-MOD: An application of the Open-Source Energy Modeling System (OSeMOSYS). *Energies*. 10(10). DOI: 10.3390/en10101468.
 17. Makhorin, A. 2008. Modeling language GNU MathProg: language reference for GLPK version 4.34. *Language*. 58(December):49.
 18. Makhorin, A. 2012. *GLPK - GNU Project - Free Software Foundation (FSF)*. Available: <http://www.gnu.org/software/glpk/>.
 19. Marquard, A., Ahjum, F., Bergh, C., Von Blottnitz, H., Burton, J., Cohen, B., Cunliffe, G., Dane, A., Hartley, F., Hughes, A., Ireland, G., Mc Call, B., Merven, B., Stevens, L. and Winkler, H. (2023). Exploring net zero pathways for South Africa - An initial study. [online] zivahub.uct.ac.za. Available at: https://zivahub.uct.ac.za/articles/report/Exploring_net_zero_pathways_for_South_Africa_-_An_initial_study/22189150/2 [Accessed 30 May 2024].
 20. Mccall, B., Ahjum, F., Burton, J., Hartley, F., Hughes, A., Ireland, G., Merven, B., Schers, J. and Marquard, A. (2020). South Africa's power generation future in the context of the Paris Agreement. [online] Available at: https://ebe.uct.ac.za/sites/default/files/content_migration/ebe_uct_ac_za/1135/files/2020_Paper%25209%2520Mccall%2520-%2520South%2520Africas%2520electricity%2520planning%2520in%2520context%2520of%2520the%2520Paris%2520Agreement.pdf [Accessed 30 May 2024].
 21. Mccall, B., Burton, J., Marquard, A., Hartley, F., Ahjum, F., Ireland, G. and Merven, B. (2019). Least-cost integrated resource planning and cost- optimal climate change mitigation policy: Alternatives for the South African electricity system. [online] Available at: https://ebe.uct.ac.za/sites/default/files/content_migration/ebe_uct_ac_za/1135/files/ERC
-

-
- %25202019%2520Alt%2520IRP%2520study%2520final%2520.pdf [Accessed 16 Jan. 2024].
22. Meridian. 2024. *Comparative Analysis of IRP 2023 cost assumptions* -. Available: <https://meridianeconomics.co.za/our-publications/comparative-analysis-of-irp-2023-cost-assumptions-2/>.
 23. Ninja. 2024. *Renewables*.
 24. Pierce, W. & Le Roux, M. 2023. Statistics of utility-scale power generation in South Africa FEBRUARY 2023.
 25. Presidential Climate Commission (2022). South Africa's Just Energy Transition Investment Plan (JET-IP). [online] www.climatecommission.org.za. Available at: <https://www.climatecommission.org.za/south-africas-jet-ip>.
 26. Quevedo, J. & Moya, I.H. 2022. Modeling of the dominican republic energy systems with OSeMOSYS to assess alternative scenarios for the expansion of renewable energy sources. *Energy Nexus*. 6(March):100075. DOI: 10.1016/j.nexus.2022.100075.
 27. Vimmerstedt, L., Akar, S., Mirletz, B., Sekar, A., Stright, D., Augustine, C., Beiter, P., Bhaskar, P., et al. 2022. Annual Technology Baseline: The 2022 Electricity Update.
 28. www.treasury.gov.za. (n.d.). National Treasury. [online] Available at: <https://www.treasury.gov.za/documents/national%20budget/2022/default.aspx> [Accessed 29 May 2024].
 29. Meridian Economics (2024). Review Of The Irp 2023 Comments For Submission To The Director- General Of The Department Of Mineral Resources And Energy 18 March 2024 Version 20240320.0. [online] Available at: <https://meridianeconomics.co.za/wp-content/uploads/2024/03/IRP2023-Modelling-Submission-20240318.0.p>
-
-

